

Zhe 852, a short-duration, high-yielding rice variety for double-cropped areas in China

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More than 70% of the total Yangtze River rice area in China is double-cropped.

Zhe 852, a short-duration semidwarf variety, was developed by irradiating Zhefu 802/Suweon 290 F₁ seeds with 30,000 r units of Cs¹³⁷ gamma rays. After 2 yr in regional national tests, it was released in Oct 1990 as a high-yielding

variety with multiple resistances and wide adaptability.

In transplanting experiments during 1987-89, average grain yield was 6-6.7 t/ha, 11% higher than that of the local check (Table 1). Zhe 852 is becoming popular among Yangtze River area farmers because of its high yield potential and short growth duration. It is resistant to blast and moderately resistant to bacterial blight and whitebacked planthopper.

Zhe 852 is 80 cm tall with intermediate tillering ability and 104-116 d duration (Table 2). It is awnless, medium-grained, with fully exerted panicles. It has 71.4% milling recovery, 25.1% amylose, 9.4% protein content, and acceptable cooking and eating quality. □

Table 1. Grain yield and duration of Zhe 852 in trials at different sites in China, 1987-89.

Site	Zhe 852		Check		Increase over check (%)	
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Designation	Duration (d)		Yield (t/ha)
<i>1987</i>						
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	114	5.5	Erjiufeng	114	5.1	8
Xiangtan, Hunan	106	7.7	Zhefu 802	105	6.7	16
Xingjian, Jiangxi	112	7.1	Zhefu 802	110	6.3	12
Mean	111	6.7		110	6.0	12
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	108	6.0	Zhuxi 26	109	5.5	9
Henyang, Hunan	106	8.3	Zhefu 802	106	7.2	16
<i>1988</i>						
Wuhan, Hubei	111	7.7	Yuanfengzao	111	7.1	8
Wuzhou, Jiangxi	104	6.1	Zhuxi 26	103	5.5	10
Heifei, Anhui	105	5.5	Zhefu 802	104	4.8	14
Mean	107	6.7		107	6.0	12
Wenzhou, Zhejiang	113	5.4	Zhuxi 26	112	4.6	17
Changsha, Hunan	108	5.9	Zhuxi 26	114	5.7	4
<i>1989</i>						
Wuhan, Hubei	114	7.5	Zhefu 802	113	6.7	10
Yichung, Jiangxi	116	5.4	Zhuxi 26	118	4.3	24
Jianyang, Fujian	113	5.9	Zhuxi 26	117	5.7	4
Mean	113	6.0		115	5.4	12

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characteristics of Zhe 852 at different sites in China, 1989.

Site	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	110	75	17.5	74	62	15.9	24.0
Changsha, Hunan	108	83	18.5	83	60	28.4	23.4
Wuhan, Hubei	114	78	17.0	77	65	15.1	25.0
Nanchang, Jiangxi	113	76	17.3	61	47	23.3	23.2
Wuhu, Anhui	114	81	17.7	69	58	15.0	24.8
Jianyang, Fujian	113	77	17.1	69	61	11.2	21.9
Zhejiang, Jiangsu	116	87	18.6	91	83	9.3	25.5
Mean	113	80	17.7	75	62	16.9	24.0

Kanakam (MO 11), a high-yielding, semitall variety from Kerala, India

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Kanakam is a medium-duration, red-kerneled variety with medium-bold grains derived from the cross IR 156/Ptb 33. It was released in 1990 for cultivation during the three seasons of Kerala: virippu (Apr-May to Aug-Sep), mundakan (Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan), and puncha (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr).

Kanakam performed well in multilo- cation trials from 1984 to 1987 (see table).

It is resistant to brown planthopper, blast, and rice tungro disease, and moderately resistant to stem borer, gall midge, and bacterial blight. □

Yield performance of Kanakam in Kerala, India.

Trial ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kanakam	Check variety ^b
Rice Research Station (RRS) Moncompu, 1984-87	4.8	3.4
Multilocal trial 1984-85	3.6	3.6
All India Coordinated Yield Trials		
BPHRVT ^b 1985	4.7	3.3
BPHRVT 1986	5.2	3.7
Farm trials, 1987-89	4.4	3.4
Operational Research Project (ORP) trials, 1987-89	6.1	5.8

^a Check variety was Jyothi at Moncompu RRS and MLT, Rasi for BPHRVT 1985, Vikas for BPHRVT 1986, and Pavizham for farm and ORP trials. ^b Brown planthopper resistant variety trial.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.